

Development of Dielectric Elastomer Nanocomposites as Stretchable and Flexible Actuating Materials

Zhijian Hu¹, Yu Wang², and Lizhi Sun^{2*}

¹School of Transportation
Wuhan University of Technology

²Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering
University of California, Irvine ([*lsun@uci.edu](mailto:lsun@uci.edu))

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Dielectric elastomers (DEs) are...

- One type of “Smart Materials”
- Dielectric elastomers change their size, and shape when subjected to applied electric fields.

Advantages and Disadvantages

- Large deformation
- Fast response speed
- Good efficiency
- Low cost
- Lightweight
- Highly inert
- But, it requires extremely high voltage to actuate DE materials...

Primary Challenge

Carbon Nanotubes

- High aspect ratio
- High electrical and thermal conductivity
- High strength

Introduction of MWNTs to DEs is one of the first attempts.

Materials

- **HS III RTV High Strength**
- **Mold-making Silicone Rubber (Alumilite)**
- **MWNTs (CheapTubes, Inc.)**
- **Conductive Carbon Grease (MG chemicals)**
- **RTV 60-CON Adhesive Sealant (Stockwell Elastomerics, Inc.)**

http://www.amazon.com/Alumilite-High-Strength-Making-Rubber/dp/B007RGE0B6/ref=pd_sim_ac_4?ie=UTF8&refRID=1J2A514KXBRQD4F47MVY

http://www.cheaptubes.com/MWNTs.htm#multi_walled_nanotubes-mwnts-20-30nm_specifications

<http://www.digikey.com/product-detail/en/846-80G/473-1121-ND/2233038>

Materials Fabrication

160 μm

Spin Coating

Molding

Compliant Electrodes

- The mixture of carbon grease and RTV 60-CON Adhesive sealant was air sprayed on the surface of the dielectric elastomer film.
- The electrode thickness was controlled to be about $20\mu\text{m}$.

<http://www.tpcglobal.com/airbrushdepot/itemdetail.aspx?itemno=MAS+S622-L>

Dispersion of Carbon Nanotubes

- To break van der Waals force, acetone and ultra-sonication are utilized.

Ultra-sonication device

20kHz, 130 W

Processing

Dispersion of Carbon Nanotubes

DE nanocomposites filled with MWNTs

Small amount of MWNTs greatly increases the stiffness and damping of DEs.

DE nanocomposites filled with MWNTs

Cross Section of a Fractured Surface
DE nanocomposites with 0.75 wt. % MWNTs

Small amount of MWNTs significantly increases the dielectric constant of DEs.

Conventional Electromechanical Measurements

-Video or CCD cameras were used to capture the area change. (e.g., Pelrine 2000, Yuan 2009)

-Then area expansion was converted to thickness strain under the incompressibility assumption. (e.g., Pelrine 2000, Choi 2014)

Electric field is applied.

Electrical \leftrightarrow Mechanical

Laser Doppler Vibrometer

Temperature: 24°C

DIRECTLY detect the thickness strain of dielectric elastomers

Laser Doppler Vibrometer Setup

Surface Displacement Measurement

25.5 V/ μm
is applied.

4.5 mm

Roughness of Compliant Electrodes

Roughness: $\pm 1.3 \mu\text{m}$ at maximum
within $115 \mu\text{m} \times 115 \mu\text{m}$ area

***Roughness of the electrodes does not
affect the displacement measurement.***

Experimental Results

The thickness strain does not depend on the boundary conditions in our setting.

Experimental Results

Deformed about 300 %
under the same applied
electric field

Experimental Results

~30 % decrease in
the required applied
electric field

Conclusions

- DE nanocomposites filled with MWNTs are developed as smart materials for actuators and energy harvesting.
- MWNTs are demonstrated to be effective in improving the electromechanical properties of DE nanocomposites.

